

2nd European Congress of Health Sciences

May 4-5, 2024 - Bristow, VA / USA (ONLINE)
medjeur.com/congress

Oral Presentation-19

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11095835

Cholecystolithiasis with Coexisted Choledocholithiasis

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ABSTRACT

Choledocholithiasis frequently accompanies symptomatic cholecystolithiasis and appropriate treatment of choledocholithiasis plays a central role in the management of these cases. Preoperative ERCP, laparoendoscopic rendezvous, and laparoscopic common bile duct exploration are currently widely used treatment options. Although the reduction of perioperative morbidity is one of the main goals of the choice of treatment modality, this choice is often based on the experience of the institutions.

Background and Aim: Choledocholithiasis accompanies cholecystolithiasis in 8-20% of cases. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy has become the standard for the treatment of symptomatic gallbladder stones, but there is no consensus on the management of cases with choledocholithiasis. With this mini-review, we aimed to evaluate the methods used in the treatment of cholecystolithiasis accompanied by choledocholithiasis with current literature.

Preoperative Endoscopic Retrograde Cholangiopancreatography (ERCP): ERCP is an advanced endoscopic method that has been widely used for a long time and choledocholithiasis is the most common indication for ERCP. Preoperative ERCP can be used to treat choledocholithiasis with a success rate of over 90%, and patients can be treated with laparoscopic cholecystectomy for cholecystolithiasis after the relief of the symptoms associated with the complication of choledocholithiasis. The frequency of unnecessary ERCP has decreased considerably with the lowering of its diagnostic use in the past and improvements in radiological diagnostic methods. Preoperative ERCP is currently the most common and widely used method in cases of cholecystolithiasis accompanied by choledocholithiasis. The most important disadvantage of preoperative ERCP is the possibility of recurrence of choledocholithiasis and other biliary symptoms during the waiting period for the operation. Recurrent biliary events have been reported with a rate exceeding 20% during the waiting period for the operation after ERCP. In addition, operation-related morbidity increases with recurrent biliary events. Therefore, laparoendoscopic rendezvous (LERV) and laparoscopic common bile duct exploration (LCBDE), two current methods for the synchronous treatment of choledocholithiasis with cholecystolithiasis, are increasing in popularity.

Laparoscopy Common Bile Duct Exploration: Although LCBDE was first performed about 30 years ago, it has become widespread only with the increase in laparoscopic technique and experience. With LCBDE, cases of choledocholithiasis can be treated with a single-stage surgical procedure. The procedure can be performed transististically or transcholedochally. LCBDE has been reported to shorten the length of stay and reduce hospital costs compared to preoperative ERCP. In addition, patients receive anesthesia only once with this method. However, postoperative bile leakage has been reported more frequently in LCBDE cases compared to preoperative ERCP. The most important disadvantage is that it requires specific and long-term training. Therefore, it has not yet been widely used.